

Formal Concept Analysis: Theory and Applications J.UCS Special Issue

Bernhard Ganter

(Technische Universität Dresden, Germany
ganter@math.tu-dresden.de)

Gerd Stumme

(Universität Kassel, Germany
stumme@cs.uni-kassel.de)

Rudolf Wille

(Technische Universität Darmstadt, Germany
wille@mathematik.tu-darmstadt.de)

Formal Concept Analysis arose around 1980 out of attempts of restructuring lattice theory to promote better communication between lattice theorists and potential users of lattice theory. Since then Formal Concept Analysis has been increasingly developed as a strong field of research stimulated by a broad spectrum of applications. Today researchers from all over the world contribute to Formal Concept Analysis and apply methods and results of Formal Concept Analysis.

Although Formal Concept Analysis has increasingly become a topic at many computer science conferences, it was only in the year 2003 when a first international conference was set up by the editors of this volume, that exclusively addressed Formal Concept Analysis. The First International Conference on Formal Concept Analysis (ICFCA 2004) was held in Darmstadt, Germany in spring 2003, and started a series of annual conferences on the state of the art of this promising field of research and applications.

Inspired by the presentations and discussions, we decided to publish a volume in the Springer State of the Art series, and a special issue of the Journal of Universal Computer Science, both aiming at presenting current research on theory and applications of Formal Concept Analysis. For the special issue of the Journal of Universal Computer Science, we called for extended versions of presentations of ICFCA, as well as for other high quality submissions. In the review process, six papers were finally selected for publication. We believe that this collection of articles illustrates well the large spectrum of research ranging from theory to applications of Formal Concept Analysis.

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Bernhard Ganter, Gerd Stumme, Rudolf Wille